

ISic3174

I.Sicily inscription 3174

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

decree (?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Ortygia, Apollonion/Artemision

Coordinates**Current Location**

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645504

PHI 329710

PHI 336189

Bibliography

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